

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

An overview on herbal peel off mask

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Abstract

The present study aims to create and test an herbal peel-off mask using natural ingredients like pineapple, turmeric, aloe vera, rice water, rose water, and glycerin. This product is designed to be effective, safe, and eco-friendly. The mask is made to clean, detoxify, and renew the skin without the harmful effects of synthetic beauty products. Pineapple extract, which contains bromelain and vitamin C, helps to exfoliate and brighten the skin by removing dead skin cells and impurities. Turmeric extract, rich in curcumin, offers strong anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antibacterial benefits that help reduce acne and skin blemishes. Aloe vera gel and glycerin act as natural moisturizers, keeping the skin hydrated and calm, while rice water and rose water add a refreshing feel and give the skin a natural shine. Evaluation showed favorable pH, texture, drying time, and skin compatibility. It provides a natural, cost-effective, and sustainable option compared to chemical-based skincare products.

Keywords: Herbal Peel-Off Mask; Pineapple Extract; Turmeric Extract; Aloe Vera; Antioxidant; Skin Rejuvenation

1. Introduction

Herbal cosmetics are beauty products that use natural plant-based ingredients to provide benefits like making skin brighter, reducing inflammation, keeping it hydrated, nourishing it, and helping to reduce signs of aging.

These products help protect and improve the health of the skin. A peel-off mask is a type of treatment where a thin layer is applied to the face. Once it dries, it forms a film that can be easily peeled off, which helps remove dirt and impurities, clean out the pores, and tighten the skin. It also helps improve blood circulation, activates skin cells, and aids in removing pollutants from the skin. Acne is a common long-term skin condition that affects the oil glands. It mostly occurs in people between the ages of 12 and 25. According to a report called the Global Burden of Disease, about 85 % of teenagers and young adults suffer from acne vulgaris [1]. The main bacteria that cause acne are Propionibacterium acnes and Staphylococcus epidermidis, and both of these are known to be resistant to many antibiotics. In countries like Indonesia, traditional medicine has been using herbal plants for treating acne for a long time [2]. Peel-off facial masks are popular because they are easy to use and help reduce the size of pores, support skin healing, and make the skin look refreshed and rejuvenated. They act as both a cleanser and a refreshing treatment, and they may also help relax facial muscles [3].

Pineapple (*Ananas comosus* L. Merr.), which belongs to the family Bromeliaceae, is a tropical fruit that is valued for its high vitamin C content and bromelain, which helps exfoliate the skin and make it brighter [4–6]. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.), a traditional medicinal plant, is well known for its curcuminoids, which have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory,

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antimicrobial, and wound-healing properties [7–16]. These natural ingredients make herbal peel-off masks a good alternative to synthetic cosmetics.

2. Plant Morphology

2.1. Plant Morphology of Pineapple

The pineapple, *Ananas comosus* L., is a perennial plant in the family Bromeliaceae, found naturally in tropical and subtropical areas. It has a short, thick stem with many long, stiff, narrow leaves that grow closely together in a tight circle. The plant is well-suited for hot and dry climates because its thick, waxy leaves and fleshy tissues help it hold onto water [17,18].

Figure 1 Pineapple

Its root system is made up of thin, fibrous roots that grow close to the surface, usually within the top 15 to 30 cm of soil, which helps it quickly take in water and nutrients. The stem, also known as the corm, is thick and fleshy and acts as a storage area for food and water. The leaves are long, ranging from 30 to 100 cm in length, with a sword-like shape and spiral arrangement. At the top of the plant, the inflorescence grows, which has 100 to 200 bisexual flowers that develop into one big, composite fruit [17,18]. The pineapple fruit is shaped like a cylinder, made from the joining of many small berries. It has a scaly outer layer and a fibrous, yellow fruit pulp that contains bromelain and sugars. Most commercial pineapple varieties are seedless and are grown through vegetative methods like using the crown, slips, or suckers [18].

2.2. Plant Morphology of Turmeric

Figure 2 Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* Linn)

Turmeric, *Curcuma longa* Linn., is a perennial herb from the Zingiberaceae family that has aromatic rhizomes [19]. The underground rhizome is yellow to orange in color because of the compound curcumin, and it serves as the main storage and reproductive part of the plant. The above-ground part looks like a stem, but it's actually formed by rolled leaf

sheaths. The leaves are large, spear-shaped, and grow in two rows. The inflorescence comes either from the rhizome or the stem, forming a spike made of bracts that hold yellowish-white flowers [19].

The plant rarely produces fruits, and it's mainly propagated through rhizomes. The rhizome contains curcuminoids and essential oils like turmerone, Atlan tone, and zingiberene, which are responsible for its medicinal and cosmetic uses [20].

Figure 3 Peel-Off Mask

3. Peel-Off Mask

Herbal cosmetics are natural beauty products made from plant-based ingredients that help heal, calm, nourish, and improve the skin. They help protect, refresh, and repair the skin. Acne is a common skin issue among people aged 18-25, often causing discomfort and lowering confidence. Using herbal formulations is helpful because they are safe, effective, and gentle for sensitive skin [23].

A peel-off mask is a thin liquid or gel that you apply to your face and let dry, forming a film that you can easily peel off. This process deeply cleanses your pores, removes dirt and dead skin cells, tightens and refreshes the skin, and improves blood circulation and cell activity. Herbal peel-off masks also deliver essential vitamins and nutrients to deeper layers of the skin, promoting nourishment and a natural glow [23].

3.1. Types of Peel-Off Masks

Modern cosmetic masks are generally divided into four types [24]

- Peel-Off Masks – Applied as a thin film, dried, and peeled to remove dead skin cells.
- Sheet Masks – Sheets soaked in serum that offer specific benefits like brightening or anti-aging.
- Leave-On Masks – Cream or gel-based masks that give deep hydration.
- Charcoal/Clay Masks – Natural cleansers and detoxifiers.

3.2. Types of Facial Skin Suitable for Peel-Off Masks

Peel-off masks work well for oily, dry, sensitive, and normal skin types [25].

4. Benefits And Advantages

4.1. Benefits of Applying Face Masks [26]

- Herbal face masks provide several skincare benefits by delivering essential nutrients to the skin.
- They nourish the skin, help reduce acne and blackheads, and remove dead skin cells.
- Face masks also create a calming and relaxing effect while restoring the skin's natural glow and brightness in a short time [26].

4.2. Advantages of Peel-Off Masks [27,28]

- Peel-off masks offer many cosmetic and therapeutic benefits.
- They help repair and revitalize the skin, improve hydration, and enhance the overall tone of the skin.
- These masks tighten pores, reduce wrinkles, and can be used for both cleansing and moisturizing.
- They are suitable for all skin types and effectively remove blackheads, whiteheads, and dead skin cells, leading to smoother and healthier skin.

4.3. Right Way to Use a Peel-Off Mask

To get the best results, use a peel-off mask correctly by following these simple steps [29]

- Gently clean your face with a suitable facial cleanser to remove dirt and oil.
- Apply the peel-off mask evenly across your face, making sure the layer is consistent.
- Let the mask dry completely for about 15 minutes.
- Carefully peel it off starting from the edges.
- Rinse your face with cold water to close the pores and refresh the skin.

4.4. Face skin problems and their causes

- Facial skin is constantly exposed to environmental and body-related factors that can lead to various skin problems. The main skin issues and their causes are as follows [30]
- Acne and Pimples – Caused by excessive oil production, clogged pores due to dead skin and dirt, bacterial infection (*Propionibacterium acnes*), and hormonal imbalance.
- Blackheads and Whiteheads – Occur from the buildup of sebum, keratin, and dead skin in pores, poor facial hygiene, and exposure to pollution and dust.
- Dull and Uneven Skin Tone – Happens due to the accumulation of dead skin, pollution, UV damage, and lack of exfoliation.
- Excess Oil and Greasiness – Caused by overactive oil glands, hormonal factors, and heavy use of makeup.
- Aging Signs (Fine Lines and Wrinkles) – Result from decreased collagen production, sun exposure, and damage from free radicals.
- Dry and Rough Skin – Caused by moisture loss, environmental stress, and dehydration.

5. Material And Methods

The herbal peel-off mask was made using natural ingredients that have been proven to be good for the skin and body. Each ingredient was chosen for its special job and how well it works with the others.

Figure 4 Pineapple

5.1. Pineapple (*Ananas comosus* L.)

- **Biological Source:** Pineapple consists of the fresh or dried fruit of *Ananas comosus* (L.) Mer
- **Family:** *Bromeliaceae*
- **Synonym:** *Ananas comosus* (L.)
- **Part To be used:** Fruit pulp
- It has bromelain, vitamin C, flavonoids, and organic acids.

- It helps with digestion, reduces inflammation, protects against free radicals, and brightens the skin, helping to remove dead skin and repair tissues.

5.2. Turmeric (*Curcuma longa* L.)

- **Biological Source:** Turmeric consists of the dried rhizomes of *Curcuma longa* Linn
- **Family:** Zingiberoside
- **Synonym:** *Curcuma longa* L.
- **Part To be used:** Roots

Figure 5 Turmeric

- It contains curcuminoids like curcumin, desmethoxycurcumin, and bisdemethoxycurcumin, along with volatile oils.
- It helps with reducing inflammation, protecting against free radicals, killing bacteria, and healing wounds, which can prevent acne and improve the skin's look.

5.3. Aloe Vera (*Aloe vera* L. Burm. f.)

Figure 6 Aloe Vera

- **Biological Source:** Aloe gel consists of the mucilaginous gel obtained from the fresh leaves of *Aloe vera* (L.) Burm. F.
- **Family:** *Asphodelaceae*
- **Synonym:** *Aloe vera* (L.) Burm. F.
- **Part To be used:** Leaves

5.3.1. Use

- It has ace Mannan, glucomannan, vitamins A, C, and E, along with minerals.
- It helps to keep the skin hydrated, reduce inflammation, heal wounds, and soothe the skin.

5.4. Glycerin

- **Synonym:** - Glycerol, Propane-1,2,3-triol, 1,2,3- Propanetriol, E422 (as a food additive code)

- **Molecular formula:** - C₃H₈O₃
- **Molecular weight:** - 92.09 g/mol
- **Chemical name:** - Propane-1,2,3-triol

5.4.1. Properties

- Physical appearance: Clear, colorless, viscous liquid with a sweet taste.
- Odor: Odorless.
- Solubility: Miscible with water, alcohol, and most polar solvents; insoluble in oils.
- Boiling Point: 290 °C.
- Melting Point: 18.2 °C.
- Density: Approximately 1.26 g/cm³.
- Hygroscopic: Absorbs moisture from the air.

5.4.2. Chemical Structure

Figure 7 Glycerine

- **Uses:** Cosmetic Industry: A key ingredient in moisturizers, creams, and lotions for its hydrating properties.
- This is a moisturizer that helps prevent dryness and improves the smoothness of the mask.

5.5. Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA)

This acts as the base that forms a film, giving the mask its peel-off feature

- **Type:** Synthetic polymer (polyhydroxy compound)
- **Molecular Formula:** (C₂H₄O)_n
- **Molecular Weight:** Varies with degree of polymerization (commonly 20,000–200,000)
- **Chemical Structure**

Figure 8 Polyvinyl Alcohol

5.5.1. Uses

- Binder in tablets and capsules
- Film-forming agent in coatings
- Viscosity enhancer in ophthalmic solutions and gels
- This improves the strength, thickness, and stability of the formulation.

5.6. Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP)

- **Type:** Synthetic, water-soluble polymer
- **Molecular Formula:** (C₆H₉NO)_n

- **Molecular Weight:** 10,000 – 700,000 (depending on grade, e.g., PVP K-30, K-90, etc.)

5.6.1. Chemical Structure

Figure 9 Polyvinylpyrrolidone

5.6.2. Uses

- Binder in tablet formulations
- Disintegrant (in cross-linked form – Crosspointe)

6. Xanthan Gum

- **Molecular structure:** β -D-glucose backbone (like cellulose) with trisaccharide side chains
- **Chemical Formula:** $(C_{35}H_{49}O_{29})_n$

6.1. Chemical Structure

Figure 10 Xanthan Gum

6.1.1. Uses

- Suspending agent – Maintains uniform dispersion of insoluble particles
- Thickening agent – Used in gels, creams, syrups, and lotions
- Stabilizer and emulsifier – Enhance viscosity and stability of formulations
- This helps thicken and stabilize the mixture, ensuring it has a smooth texture.

6.2. Methyl Paraben

6.2.1. Chemical Nature

- Type: Synthetic ester (alkyl ester of p-hydroxybenzoic acid)
- Chemical Name: Methyl p-hydroxybenzoate
- Molecular Formula: $C_8H_8O_3$
- Molecular Weight: 152.15 g/mol

6.2.2. Chemical Structure

Figure 11 Methyl Paraben

6.2.3. Uses

- Widely used as an antimicrobial preservative in oral, topical, and parenteral formulations.
- Effective against fungi and some bacteria.

6.3. Propyl Paraben [32]

- **Chemical Name:** Propyl p-hydroxybenzoate
- **Molecular Formula:** C₁₀H₁₂O₃
- **Molecular Weight:** 180.20 g/mol
- **Chemical Structure:**

Figure 12 Propyl Paraben

6.3.1. Uses

Used as a preservative in

- Oral preparations: Syrups, suspensions
- Topical preparations: Creams, ointments, gels, and lotions

6.4. Rice Water (*Oryza sativa* L.)

- **Biological Source:** Rice water is the starchy water obtained after soaking or boiling rice (*Oryza sativa* Linn.), a member of the family *Poaceae*. It contains water-soluble vitamins, minerals, amino acids, and carbohydrates derived from rice grains.

Biological Name: *Oryza sativa* Linn.

Figure 13 Rice Water

- **Family:** Pinaceae (Gramineae)
- **Part of plant:** seed
- **Common Names:** Transduodenal

6.4.1. Uses

- Skin care: Natural cleanser, toner, and moisturizer; improves skin texture and elasticity.
- Hair care: Strengthens roots, promotes growth, and adds shine; used in herbal shampoos and conditioners.
- Anti-inflammatory: Soothes irritated or sunburned skin
- This contains starch, vitamins B1–B3, and minerals.
- It helps improve the skin's color and elasticity.

6.5. Rose Water

- **Synonym:** Rose Hydrosol, Rose floral Water
- **Family:** *Rosaceae*
- **Parts To be used:** Rose Petals
- **Medicinal Uses:** Acne treatment, Toner, eye Car.

6.5.1. Use

- This serves as a natural toner and adds a pleasant fragrance.
- It also has mild anti-inflammatory properties.

7. Formulation

The herbal peel-off mask was made using a simple mixing and heating method [33].

7.1. Method

- All the ingredients were measured accurately.
- Methyl paraben and propyl paraben were dissolved in rice water.
- The film-forming agents, PVA and PVP, were dissolved separately in warm water.
- Extracts from pineapple, turmeric, and aloe vera were added to the film-forming solution.
- The preservative solution was mixed into the other ingredients.
- Glycerin was added to prevent dryness.
- Rose water was added for fragrance.
- The mixture was stirred for 20 minutes to make it uniform.
- The final product was put into sealed containers with labels.

Table 1 Ingredient used in formulation

Sr. No	Ingredient	Function
1	Pineapple Extract	Anti-Acne and Antibacterial
2	Turmeric Extract	Anti-inflammatory and antibacterial
3	Aloe Vera Gel	Moisturize
4	Glycerine	prevents dryness
5	Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA)	Film-forming base (peel-off agent)
6	Polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVP K-30)	Improves peel strength and texture
7	Xanthan Gum	Thickener and stabilizer
8	Methyl Paraben	Preservative
9	Propyl Paraben	Preservative
10	Rose Water	Solvent and vehicle
11	Rice Water	Moisturizer and brightener

8. Evaluation Parameters

The herbal peel-off mask was tested for its physical and performance traits using standard methods [33].

8.1. pH Determination

The pH of the mask was checked using a digital pH meter that was calibrated with buffer solutions at pH 4, 7, and 9. The pH was found to be suitable for applying on the skin.

8.2. Physical Evaluation

The formulation was checked for colour, consistency, texture, greasiness, and smell. It had a smooth texture, looked uniform, and smelled pleasant.

8.3. Peel-Off Test

The gel was spread evenly on the face and allowed to dry. It took 18 minutes to dry, and the film peeled off easily without tearing, which shows good strength and flexibility.

8.4. Washability

The mask was easy to wash off with water, proving it has good cleansing and removal properties.

8.5. Irritation Test

A patch test was done to check skin compatibility. No redness, itching, or irritation was seen, confirming the formulation is not irritating.

8.6. Spread ability

Spread ability (S) was calculated using the formula:

$$S = (m \times l) / t$$

8.6.1. were

- S = Spread ability
- m = mass
- l = length
- t = time

9. Conclusion

This study successfully created and tested an herbal peel-off mask using natural ingredients like pineapple, turmeric, aloe vera, rice water, rose water, and glycerin. The product showed a good pH, texture, drying time, spreadability, and was non-irritating, making it suitable for use on the face. The pineapple extract, which has bromelain and vitamin C, gives exfoliating and brightening effects. The turmeric extract, rich in curcumin, provides anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antibacterial effects. Aloe vera and glycerin help with moisturizing and soothing the skin. Rice water and rose water contribute to skin toning and freshness. In conclusion, the herbal peel-off mask is a safe, effective, and eco-friendly skincare product. It offers deep cleansing, detoxification, and rejuvenation benefits. It is a natural and affordable alternative to synthetic skincare products, and it works well for all skin types, especially those with acne, dullness, or uneven skin tone.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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